

Factoring of the Smarandache Back Concatenated Prime Sequence,
by Micha Fleuren

SmBackConpri(1): 2
PRIME!

SmBackConpri(2): 32
 2^5

SmBackConpri(3): 532
 $2^2 \cdot 7 \cdot 19$

SmBackConpri(4): 7532
 $2^2 \cdot 7 \cdot 269$

SmBackConpri(5): 117532
 $2^2 \cdot 29383$

SmBackConpri(6): 13117532
 $2^2 \cdot 89 \cdot 36847$

SmBackConpri(7): 1713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 7 \cdot 3559 \cdot 17191$

SmBackConpri(8): 191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 47928279383$

SmBackConpri(9): 23191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 41 \cdot 43 \cdot 59 \cdot 389 \cdot 143291$

SmBackConpri(10): 2923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 3 \cdot 17 \cdot 31189 \cdot 459436697$

SmBackConpri(11): 312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 53 \cdot 20399 \cdot 72359075989$

SmBackConpri(12): 37312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 19 \cdot 47 \cdot 967 \cdot 52127 \cdot 207232859$

SmBackConpri(13): 4137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 137 \cdot 83231 \cdot 902903 \cdot 100464263$

SmBackConpri(14): 434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 914314771 \cdot 118705648944173$

SmBackConpri(15): 47434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 11 \cdot 79 \cdot 401 \cdot 18911 \cdot 1799502156431237$

SmBackConpri(16): 5347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 3 \cdot 19^2 \cdot 1331343719 \cdot 927185865807779$

SmBackConpri(17): 595347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 233199983486549 \cdot 638237002889467$

SmBackConpri(18): 61595347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 3 \cdot 7 \cdot 67 \cdot 10944446949917788365883388969$

SmBackConpri(19): 6761595347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 29 \cdot 67 \cdot 229 \cdot 30223 \cdot 125702330968313339824643$

SmBackConpri(20): 716761595347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 3^3 \cdot 137 \cdot 197 \cdot 439009 \cdot 560132477971759195558729$

SmBackConpri(21): 73716761595347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 101 \cdot 383 \cdot 2663 \cdot 128615477 \cdot 5501034529 \cdot 252858372919$

SmBackConpri(22): 7973716761595347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 1993429190398836858534328230797928279383$

SmBackConpri(23): 837973716761595347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 10464659 \cdot 28705217 \cdot 697404090649644703846964461$

SmBackConpri(24): 89837973716761595347434137312923191713117532
 $2^2 \cdot 3^2 \cdot 127213543 \cdot 2804581952317 \cdot 699448855524114980477$

SmBackConpri(25): 9789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.197.7724551.88861823.18099260181707709142763088643
SmBackConpri(26): 1019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3^4.79.107.239.251.69529011899.89272381571089300541521021
SmBackConpri(27): 1031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.23.536742221.107378899223.194443964630034339400965929987
SmBackConpri(28): 1071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3.15080897595271451.5918254163496956084117930827951465511
SmBackConpri(29):
1091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.29.2221.127481.2141791.3025029911203.5127365219443127603244941299
SmBackConpri(30):
1131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3^3.39119.106163.2521813072352606862649520505665026319146564133657
SmBackConpri(31):
1271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.431.442211844520806651488997100381.1667334394495053279832359694253
SmBackConpri(32):
1311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3.109272594257589252584982486497809730132945619511442743599309426461
SmBackConpri(33):
1371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.298559830808507.52214235459538126367.21991545686151602277989934845676
107
SmBackConpri(34):
1391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3.11.4132061.25509526001803999062948926583981499747227205403532723399
85115491
SmBackConpri(35):
1491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117
532

2^2.24972581.239987353.37382801369.11017221868993.14764017937341161.10231
312408849725763
SmBackConpri(36):
1511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713
117532

2^2.3.97.29753759636927.34428589521936380359.1267627396063159752254597521
298801282176741
SmBackConpri(37):
1571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191
713117532

2^2.53.16224701.456882999183336786528870419835800672012918431430151783530
159184534497911

SmBackConpri(38):

1631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923
191713117532

2^2.71.23173.516034084311583.48042668715891435645848927808272485600591342
0246751090313730147

SmBackConpri(39):

1671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312
923191713117532

2^2.41.101928754360456792156787272629944577501891450599876446143999716306
95959225141412884863

SmBackConpri(40):

1731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137
312923191713117532

2^2.3^2.9996754732603.481176052154180505414306100531857616152329812927703
5312379012563518594410029

SmBackConpri(41):

1791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434
137312923191713117532

2^2.7.11.64381.9046249.11590180635232296517875131.86179861894193529229607
6703869131742056941533339330261

SmBackConpri(42):

1811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595347
434137312923191713117532

2^2.3^2.78479.95564446769525778571883.118424859029914429947871871.5666476
4175929782392855189371183968207021

SmBackConpri(43):

1911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761595
347434137312923191713117532

2^2.137.608987837.116713367662855148561752006884036975853579.490834813313
44753518433092671989963181080704833

SmBackConpri(44):

1931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716761
595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3.9446164153167567389.1699531357173032183195719364859241.100281629301
03906409167316224792230592116125539289

SmBackConpri(45):

1971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973716
761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.7.31.1217544413.174227539625222196340093.1070953400597882529934644521
8860369233492700379911737807330846454442711

SmBackConpri(46)*

1991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837973
716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3.23.9415971857.

c96:

7664943903810278433999376445267257659291396317990533466010410264846675872
87725060165333663336251
SmBackConpri(47):
2111991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789837
973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.4127.5023.250287803.13194506021633.2625669740708891.42670318369990190
261.6219855571269996508421.11067652638511942724814487
SmBackConpri(48)*
223211991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019789
837973716761595347434137312923191713117532
2^2.13.79.139.2411.5701.

c102:

2843953519365383369036220138046305215370041500662841841130065028626559982
70313210647905694141940453601
SmBackConpri(49)*
227223211991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031019
789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532
2^2.349861990565301958632269873

c91:

1623663168097034530369026051770320474313507442018541121125015301441158509
284822065343140871
SmBackConpri(50):
229227223211991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071031
019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.181.18593.47297.383650756287733427291486683.9384443082324230729233737
823216261020301901551838110330452800701979718008833012001
SmBackConpri(51):
233229227223211991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091071
031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.97.1358153.2840569429.5208416075069.125893549159629791635472017.15105
90974494468062986447417145361.1573044861122356605217467878578399
SmBackConpri(52):
239233229227223211991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131091
071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3^3.73.45798292013.1014773874199.1817834364259.1115370898935680022749
1284821.322019898850953993647920761543905231101642892928302951190361
SmBackConpri(53):
241239233229227223211991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271131
091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.97.8641.345497992979.71898963328847.86994872096861.1087513458692371.3
06165151706395409878521282820973266257742923702253147253427030816293
SmBackConpri(54):
251241239233229227223211991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311271
131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

2^2.3.467.12919.347027508345980392107673136503231372034222529846184251016
76616259405999561799005142498811568389935069014753201924002965537257

SmBackConpri(55)*

2572512412392332292272232111991971931911811791731671631571511491391371311
271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

$2^{2.7^{2.117797}}$.

c129:

1114210321870022803096329898561210340545994549829874929930265492794059285
00272394028217993657968749321808098234173964502444935611

SmBackConpri(56)*

2632572512412392332292272232111991971931911811791731671631571511491391371
311271131091071031019789837973716761595347434137312923191713117532

$2^{2.372121.441825557.184386550755819823}$.

c107:

2170981375945454688643659481463928987456809150361473164449019391462147699
7131463092494095331990237024618493